

Life cycle assessment of BarkBuild products

Introduction

Of the level 2 products produced in the BarkBuild project (Figure 1), a life cycle assessment (LCA) of the wood outdoor coating, low-density fibre board, and plywood boards was completed. Also assessed, were the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder and its simplified variant, suberinic acid-lignin binder. This report presents the inventories of the level 1 products, level 2 products, and their conventional counterparts. Comparisons between level 2 products and their conventional counterparts will be discussed in the results section.

Figure 1. Material flow from raw material to the end product presented as dry masses until the final amounts of products.

Level 1

Level 1 products are intermediate products sometimes referred to as industrial precursors. These are the ingredients needed to manufacture the level 2 products used by consumers. Here the following were assessed: suberinic acid, lignosulfonate lignin, kraft lignin, and polyphenols. Results are displayed in tabular format.

Table 1. Inventory of the materials, energy emissions, and waste treatment needed for production of 1 kg of suberinic acid.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Bark chips, wet, measured as dry mass {CH} bark chips production, hardwood, at sawmill Undefined Cut-off, U	2,5 kg
Ethanol, without water, in 95% solution state, from fermentation {CHkg} ethanUonld perfoindeudction from wood Cut-off, U	5,3 kg

Potassium hydroxide {RER} production Cut-off, U kg Undefined	0,67 kg
Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} tap water production, conventional Cut	550 kg
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	16,12 kWh
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater, average {CH} treatment of, capacity 5E9l/year Cut-off, U	0,55 l

Table 2. Inventory of the materials, energy emissions, and physical emissions needed for production of 1 kg of lignosulfonate lignin.

Inputs from nature	
Antimony in ground	1,99E-5 kg
Water, cooling, surface in ground	8,95E-1 ton
Gas, natural, 46.8 MJ per kg in ground Undefined	0,368 kg
Emissions to air	
Carbon dioxide, fossil	1,25 kg
Carbon dioxide, biogenic -	9,42E-1 kg
Methane, trichlorofluoro-, CFC-11	3,73E-7 kg
Nitrogen oxides	0,002558685 kg
NM VOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds, unspecified	3,58E-3kg
Emissions to water	
Sulfur dioxide	0,007938931 kg
Phosphorus	4,46E-5 kg
Nitrogen oxides	0,003161954 kg
Emissions to soil	
Carbon dioxide, to soil or biomass stock	5,89E-3 kg Undefined

Table 3. Inventory of the materials, energy emissions, and physical emissions needed for production of 1 kg kraft lignin.

Materials/fuels	
Wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass {DE} softwood forestry, pine, sustainable forest management Cut-off, U	3 ton
Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RER} market for CUuntdeffin, eUd	0,3 ton
Base oil {GLO} market for base oil Cut-off, U kg Undefined	5kg
Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} 2m4a,6rket for Cut-off, U ton Undefined	24,6 ton
Sodium hydroxide, chlor-alkali production 0m,1ix, at plant/RER ton Undefined	0,1 ton
Charcoal {GLO} market for Cut-off, U 0,5 kg Undefined	0,5 kg

Polystyrene granulate (PS)/EU-27 0,2 kg Undefined	0,2 kg
Electricity/heat	
Industrial furnace, natural gas {RER} production Cut-off, U p Undefined	0 p
Cooling energy {CH} from natural gas, at2 cogen unit with absorption chiller Cut-off, U	21,6 MJ

Table 4. Inventory of the materials, energy emissions, and physical emissions needed for production of 1 kg of polyphenols.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0,136055938 m3
Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} tap water production, conventional Cut	0,176872673 m3
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	0,965997 kWh debarking
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	0,313215 kWh bark milling
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	0,060085 kWh bark pressing
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {CH} heat production, softwood chips from forest, at furnace 5000kW, state-of-the-art 2014 Cut-off, U	2,453632 kWh bark press water evaporation / condensation to 24% m/m (heat needed for evaporation – heat produced by the “wet bark co-product” burning)
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater, average {CH} treatment of, capacity 5E9l/year Cut-off, U	0,173593 t

0,70 m3 of pulpwood softwood was debarked in a wet-debarking process in a paper pulp production plant. 0,92 m3 of water was added to the debarking drum. 278,87 kg of paper pulp was produced (co-product), 0,90 m3 water was sent to municipal waste water treatment (contains a very low amount of low-toxicity organic matter) and 126,76 m3 bark and 0,02 m3 of debarking water were taken further for:

- Milling (electricity was needed) – resulting in 126,76 kg of 20/80 suspension of milled bark in water sent for
- Pressing (electricity was needed) + 64,7 kg of 39/61 wet bark burnt for heat (resulting in 43 kWh heat + R kg of water vapour)

Which ultimately resulted in 62 l of bark press water (containing 1,61% of solid mass polyphenols).

62 l of bark press water was condensed to 5,176 l of polyphenol “black liquor” (containing 24% of dry mass polyphenols) – heat was needed and B kg of water was released into the air.

The resulting 5,176 l of polyphenol “black liquor” was used to prepare “Polyphenol-Suberinic acid-Lignin Binder” for the production of new low-density fiberboard and plywood, and “Wood outdoor coating” (together with Suberinic acids).

Level 2

Level 2 products consist of products that are sold as consumer products. In this report, this includes polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder, suberinic acid-lignin binder, wood outdoor coating and alkyd paint conventional counterpart, low-density fiberboard created with both lignin binders and conventional counterpart using phenol formaldehyde, plywood created with both lignin binders and conventional counterpart using urea-formaldehyde. Results are displayed in tabular format.

Table 5. Inventory of the materials, energy emissions, and physical emissions needed for production of 1 kg of suberinic acid-lignin binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} chlor-alkali electrolysis, membrane Undefined cell Cut-off, U NaOH	0,029585799 kg
Kraft lignin Undefined	0,059171598 kg
Lignosulfonate Undefined	0,295857988 kg
Suberinic Acid Undefined	0,00887574 kg
Sulfuric acid {RER} production Cut-off, U Undefined	0,033136095 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, kg Undefined	0,5222 kg
Glyoxal {RER} production Cut-off, U Undefined	0,079881657 kg
Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	1,14 kWh
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater, average {CH} treatment of, capacity 5E9l/year Cut-off, U	6,42 l

Table 6. Inventory of the materials needed to produce 1 kg of polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} chlor-alkali electrolysis, membrane Undefined cell Cut-off, U NaOH	0,0143 kg
Kraft lignin Undefined	0,0857 kg
Lignosulfonate Undefined	0,0857 kg
Suberinic Acid Undefined	0,1029 kg
Polyphenols	0,3429 kg
Sulfuric acid {RER} production Cut-off, U Undefined	0,016 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, kg Undefined	0,2522 kg
Glyoxal {RER} production Cut-off, U Undefined	0,1004 kg
Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	1,139 kWh

After the inventory for all components was gathered, the combined inventory was made for the Wood outdoor coating, as well as the inventories for low-density fibreboard and plywood using these two new adhesives. Furthermore, inventories were made for conventional coatings, plywood, and fiberboard.

Table 7. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed to produce 2,5 kg of the wood outdoor coating.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Suberinic Acid Undefined	2 kg
Polyphenols	0,5 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, kg Undefined	0,2225 kg
Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	2,3375 kWh
Electricity(total)	2,3375 kWh
Stirrer	0,0216 kWh Dissolving + solvent exchange
Centrifuge	0,0396 kWh Concentrating acidified polyphenol + removing undissolved part
Centrifuge	0,4500 kWh Concentrating hybrid particles
Vortex	0,0575 kWh +
Ultrasound	0,0067 kWh Redispersing hybrid particles
Rotavap	1,7621 kWh Recovering ethanol
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater, average {CH} treatment of, capacity 5E9l/year Cut-off, U	0,1864 l

There were two assumptions made in making up this inventory (Table 7). First, that all alcohol (EtOH), acting as a solvent, will be reused in a “closed loop” (evaporation on a rotavapor), without any losses, and secondly, that all the waste water types that are made in the processes have such a small quantity of inorganic and organic constituents in them that it can all be processed in a municipal waste water treatment plant. Therefore, they were pooled together into a one-line item.

Table 8. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed to produce 1 m3 of the New Low-density fibreboard (Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder)

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Chemical, organic {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,97683834 kg
Dust collector, electrostatic precipitator, for industrial use {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	5,14666E-06 p
Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0,304711128 kg
Paraffin {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	9,250870532 kg
Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder	12,53099621 kg
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,011279915 m3

Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0,406010966 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,012847248 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,460286747 m3
Saw dust, wet, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	19,70664455 kg
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,008962092 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	1253,697094 kg
Vegetable oil, refined {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	4,232099006 kg
Wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass {RER} market for Cut-off, U	205,0327495 kg
Wood chips, from post-consumer wood, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,92267486 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	3,79348E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	2,240523003 m3
Electricity/heat	
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,82309606 MJ
Electricity, medium voltage {AT} market for Cut-off, U	17,09767998 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {DE} market for Cut-off, U	338,4334891 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {FR} market for Cut-off, U	21,62353645 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {HU} market for Cut-off, U	28,66375762 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PL} market for Cut-off, U	27,1551388 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PT} market for Cut-off, U	16,0919341 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	53,80740465 kWh
Furnace, wood chips, softwood storage area, 1000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,57185E-05 p
Furnace, wood chips, with silo, 5000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,000108695 p
Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, natural gas, at boiler condensing modulating >100kW Cut-off, U	0,026364673 MJ
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, at hard coal industrial furnace 1-10MW Cut-off, U	3428,355833 MJ
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {GLO} heat production, wood chips from post-consumer wood, at furnace 300kW Cut-off, U	18,9673905 MJ
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from hard fibreboard production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,220607243 m3
Biowaste {CH} market for Cut-off, U	93,60407212 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,004418799 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {Europe without Switzerland} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,169047471 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {CH} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	0,037053398 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {Europe without Switzerland} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	1,814987612 kg

Table 9. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed for the production of 1 m3 of the New Low-density fibreboard (Suberinic acids-Lignin binder)

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Chemical, organic {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,97683834 kg
Dust collector, electrostatic precipitator, for industrial use {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	5,14666E-06 p
Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0,304711128 kg
Paraffin {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	9,250870532 kg
Suberinic acid-Lignin Binder	12,53099621 kg
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,011279915 m3
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0,406010966 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,012847248 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,460286747 m3
Saw dust, wet, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	19,70664455 kg
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,008962092 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	1253,697094 kg
Vegetable oil, refined {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	4,232099006 kg
Wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass {RER} market for Cut-off, U	205,0327495 kg
Wood chips, from post-consumer wood, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,92267486 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	3,79348E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	2,240523003 m3
Electricity/heat	
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,82309606 MJ
Electricity, medium voltage {AT} market for Cut-off, U	17,09767998 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {DE} market for Cut-off, U	338,4334891 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {FR} market for Cut-off, U	21,62353645 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {HU} market for Cut-off, U	28,66375762 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PL} market for Cut-off, U	27,1551388 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PT} market for Cut-off, U	16,0919341 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	53,80740465 kWh
Furnace, wood chips, softwood storage area, 1000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,57185E-05 p
Furnace, wood chips, with silo, 5000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,000108695 p
Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, natural gas, at boiler condensing modulating >100kW Cut-off, U	0,026364673 MJ
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, at hard coal industrial furnace 1-10MW Cut-off, U	3428,355833 MJ

Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {GLO} heat production, wood chips from post-consumer wood, at furnace 300kW Cut-off, U	18,9673905 MJ
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from hard fibreboard production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,220607243 m3
Biowaste {CH} market for Cut-off, U	93,60407212 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,004418799 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {Europe without Switzerland} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,169047471 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {CH} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	0,037053398 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {Europe without Switzerland} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	1,814987612 kg

Table 10. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed for the production of 1 m3 of the conventional low-density fibreboard using a phenolic binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Aluminium sulfate, powder {RER} market for aluminium sulfate, powder Cut-off, U	0,581540193 kg
Chemical, organic {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,97683834 kg
Dust collector, electrostatic precipitator, for industrial use {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	5,14666E-06 p
Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0,304711128 kg
Paraffin {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	9,250870532 kg
Phenolic resin {RER} market for phenolic resin Cut-off, U	11,94945602 kg
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,011279915 m3
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0,406010966 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,012847248 m3
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,460286747 m3
Saw dust, wet, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	19,70664455 kg
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,008962092 kg
Tap water {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	1253,697094 kg
Vegetable oil, refined {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	4,232099006 kg
Wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass {RER} market for Cut-off, U	205,0327495 kg
Wood chips, from post-consumer wood, measured as dry mass {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,92267486 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	3,79348E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	2,240523003 m3
Electricity/heat	
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	41,82309606 MJ
Electricity, medium voltage {AT} market for Cut-off, U	17,09767998 kWh

Electricity, medium voltage {DE} market for Cut-off, U	338,4334891 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {FR} market for Cut-off, U	21,62353645 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {HU} market for Cut-off, U	28,66375762 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PL} market for Cut-off, U	27,1551388 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {PT} market for Cut-off, U	16,0919341 kWh
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for Cut-off, U	53,80740465 kWh
Furnace, wood chips, softwood storage area, 1000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,57185E-05 p
Furnace, wood chips, with silo, 5000kW {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0,000108695 p
Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, natural gas, at boiler condensing modulating >100kW Cut-off, U	0,026364673 MJ
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} heat production, at hard coal industrial furnace 1-10MW Cut-off, U	3428,355833 MJ
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {GLO} heat production, wood chips from post-consumer wood, at furnace 300kW Cut-off, U	18,9673905 MJ
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from hard fibreboard production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,220607243 m3
Biowaste {CH} market for Cut-off, U	93,60407212 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,004418799 kg
Hazardous waste, for incineration {Europe without Switzerland} market for hazardous waste, for incineration Cut-off, U	0,169047471 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {CH} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	0,037053398 kg
Wood ash mixture, pure {Europe without Switzerland} market for wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, U	1,814987612 kg

Table 11. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed for the production of 1 m3 of BarkBuild plywood using the new polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,155529945 m3
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,946041297 m3
Polyphenol-Suberinic acid-Lignin Binder	64,75952864 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	2,59194E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	1,432181883 m3
Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	238,1780741 kWh
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,490751101 MJ

Heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas {CH} heat production, hardwood chips from forest, at furnace 50kW Cut-off, U	5049,997858 MJ
Emissions to air	
Water	0,55497048 m3
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from plywood production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,432181883 m3

Table 12. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed to produce 1 m3 of the BarkBuild Plywood using suberinic acid-lignin binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,155529945 m3
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,946041297 m3
Suberinic acid-Lignin Binder	64,75952864 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	2,59194E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	1,432181883 m3
Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	238,1780741 kWh
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,490751101 MJ
Heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas {CH} heat production, hardwood chips from forest, at furnace 50kW Cut-off, U	5049,997858 MJ
Emissions to air	
Water	0,55497048 m3
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from plywood production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,432181883 m3

Table 13. Inventory of the materials, energy, emissions, and waste treatment needed to produce 1 m3 of conventional plywood using a urea-formaldehyde binder.

Materials/Fuels/electricity	
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {CH} market for Cut-off, U	0,155529945 m3
Sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1,946041297 m3
Urea formaldehyde resin {RER} production Cut-off, U	64,75952864 kg
Wooden board factory, organic bonded boards {RER} construction Cut-off, U	2,59194E-08 p
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	1,432181883 m3

Electricity/heat	
Electricity, medium voltage {ENTSO-E} market group	238,1780741 kWh
Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	2,490751101 MJ
Heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas {CH} heat production, hardwood chips from forest, at furnace 50kW Cut-off, U	5049,997858 MJ
Emissions to air	
Water	0,55497048 m3
Waste to treatment	
Wastewater from plywood production {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1,432181883 m3

Results and discussion

Using SimaPro (version 9.1.0.11) modelling software and the above listed inventories (values derived from BarkBuild project measurements or the Ecolnvent 3 database), we calculated the environmental costs for each of the products using the method described in EN 15804 +A2 Method V1.00 / EF 3.0 which takes into consideration biogenic carbon stored in the products. These costs were expressed in 27 impact indicators (some of them are composite indicators). The complete results are presented in the attached appendices, but here only the global warming potential (GWP) will be highlighted as one of the more important indicators, especially when considering biomaterials which store carbon causing negative emissions of GWP gases. As this is a composite indicator, its components (fossil, biogenic, land use and land use change-connected emissions) are presented. The results are therefore given as a comparison of GWP of the project manufactured products with their traditional functional alternatives.

We compared the environmental (climate) performance of the outdoor wood coating with its functional alternative, alkyd paint. Furthermore, we compared a conventionally produced fiberboard and plywood panels with those where polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin OR suberinic acid-lignin binders were used. This was, in practice, done by replacing the adhesive system of the fiberboard and plywood in the SimaPro inventory with either of the new binders. This ensures that we are only comparing the effect of the component we changed, although it must be emphasized that this is a theoretical exercise. It is debatable how realistic it is that the manufacturing process of the board remains unchanged. Therefore, it must be noted that the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin Binder and suberinic acid-lignin binder, and the new low-density fiberboard and new plywood board were produced on a laboratory scale. Consequently, the values obtained for the environmental impacts for these products were very likely higher than they would have been in the eventual industrial production. The traditional binder and both types of boards, however, were assessed as produced on an industrial scale, and therefore their environmental impacts were already optimized.

The conventional fibreboard and plywood uses a binder system, which is transported from elsewhere (and that environmental impact is included) but in the case of the BarkBuild produced binders, we did not have the information of how far it would need to be transported. Therefore, we removed the transport of the binder system in both the new system and the conventional fibreboard and plywood impact assessments.

Outdoor wood coating assessment

A comparison between the BarkBuild manufactured outdoor wood coating and an alkyd paint for outdoor use was made. In Figure 2 and Figure 3 we can see the contribution of materials and processes used to produce 1 kg of either coating/paint towards their respective GWP. For the outdoor wood coating, it can be seen that the energy consumption (the most) and wastewater treatment (moderately) contributed net positive CO₂ emissions, while Polyphenols contributed to the most of sequestration of atmospheric carbon (negative CO₂ emissions), yielding overall negative emissions for the product. Conversely, we can see that the overall GWP for the alkyd paint is positive, with the highest contribution by titanium dioxide (pigment).

When compared (Table 14), it is clearly obvious that the production of the new Outdoor Wood Coating is much more environmentally- (climate-) friendly than the alkyd paint.

Table 14. Comparison of the GWP of Outdoor Wood Coating and Alkyd paint

	Outdoor Wood Coating (kg CO ₂ eq)	Alkyd paint (kg CO ₂ eq)	Difference (kg CO ₂ eq)
Climate change	-19,01776318	6,008735687	-25,0265
Climate change - Fossil	8,85515753	5,425263458	3,429894
Climate change - Biogenic	-27,92204698	-0,607296197	-27,3148
Climate change - Land use and LU change	0,049126272	1,190768425	-1,14164

Figure 2. A network diagram of Outdoor Wood Coating constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Figure 3. A network diagram of Alkyd paint constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Low-density fiberboard assessment

A comparison between the BarkBuild manufactured low-density fiberboard using a polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder as well as a suberinic acid-lignin binder with a conventional low-density fiberboard using a phenolic resin for indoor use was made. In Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6, we can see the contribution of materials and processes used to produce 1 m³ of either BarkBuild manufactured low density fiberboard towards their respective GWP. For the fiberboard using the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder (Figure 4), it can be seen that the energy consumption contributed by far the most net positive CO₂ emissions, while the initial raw material (softwood pulpwood) contributed to the most sequestration of atmospheric carbon (negative CO₂ emissions), yielding overall negative emissions for the product. A very similar situation was found with the BarkBuild fibreboards using the suberinic acid-lignin binder (Figure 5), with the main contributors (positive or negative) to its GWP are the same. Unlike with the outdoor wood coating comparison made above, we can see (Figure 6) that the overall GWP for conventional low-density fibreboard using a phenolic resin is still negative, with the highest contribution (positive or negative) by the same constituents as it was with the two new low-density fibreboards.

Figure 4. A network diagram of New Low-density fibreboard (Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Figure 5. A network diagram of New Low-density fibreboard (Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Figure 6. A network diagram of Conventional Low-density fibreboard (Phenolic resin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

When compared (Table 15), it is obvious that the production of the BarkBuild manufactured low-density fiberboard using the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin system was more environmentally (climate-) friendly than the other two fiberboards. The production of suberinic acids requires much more energy than the production of polyphenols, which contributes to a more favorable environmental footprint of the fiberboard using a polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder. In fact, there is comparatively only a small difference between the BarkBuild low-density fiberboard using the suberinic acid-lignin binder and the that using a phenolic resin binder, which was surprising, as the fossil-based binder (phenolic) was replaced by one from renewable, natural sources. While not part

of this assessment, it should be noted that phenolic binder systems typically use formaldehyde as a cross-linking agent which is a carcinogen and while it is regulated to varying degrees, improper care can harm workers and consumers.

Table 15. Comparison of the GWP of New Low-density fibreboard (Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder), and Conventional Low-density fibreboard (Phenolic resin binder).

	BarkBuild low-density fibreboard (polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder) (kg CO2 eq)	BarkBuild low-density fibreboard (suberinic acid-lignin binder) (kg CO2 eq)	Conventional low-density fibreboard (phenolic resin binder) (kg CO2 eq)
Climate change	-1019,446486	-558,277553	-526,1572192
Climate change - Fossil	868,7059138	847,1543246	871,2181015
Climate change - Biogenic	-1904,607977	-1421,55404	-1413,510692
Climate change - Land use and LU change	16,45557725	16,1221622	16,13537134

Plywood assessment

A comparison of the BarkBuild manufactured plywood using both the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder and suberinic acid-lignin binder was made with conventional plywood using a urea formaldehyde binder system. These products were made for indoor use. In Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 we can see the contribution of materials and processes used to produce 1 m³ of plywood with their varying binder systems towards their respective GWP. For the BarkBuild manufactured plywood using polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin (Figure 7), it can be seen that the energy consumption contributed the most net positive CO₂ emissions, although much of the energy needed was derived by burning wood chips, and therefore almost climate-neutral. Nevertheless, the initial raw materials (sawlogs and veneer logs) contributed to the sequestration of atmospheric carbon (negative CO₂ emissions) very similarly to the other BarkBuild binder system using polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin, yielding negative emissions for the product. Conversely, with suberinic acid-lignin binder system (Figure 8), the main positive contributors to its GWP is still the energy needed for its production (although also largely derived by burning wood chips), but the main negative contributor was only its initial raw material (sawlogs and veneer logs). Therefore, the overall negative CO₂ emissions are lower. Unlike with the fiberboards compared in the previous section, we can see (Figure 8) that positive contributions came from both energy demand and the urea formaldehyde binder (the latter became more prominent, as the former are lower due to almost climate-neutral burning of wood chips). The overall GWP for the conventional plywood using urea formaldehyde is still negative, and this is due to very high negative CO₂ sequestration of the initial raw materials (sawlogs and veneer logs) through atmospheric carbon bound in wood.

Figure 7. A network diagram of New Plywood board (Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Figure 8. A network diagram of New Plywood board (Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

Figure 9. A network diagram of Conventional Plywood board (Urea formaldehyde resin binder) constituents' contributions to its overall GWP.

When compared (Table 16), it is apparent that the production of the BarkBuild plywood using the polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder is more environmentally- (climate-) friendly than the other two plywood variants. Like with the fiberboard comparisons, there is only a small difference between the suberinic acid-lignin binder and the conventional plywood made using urea formaldehyde, which again shows that the suberinic acid-lignin binder is not much better in the environmental (climate) sense than the fossil-based binder, although it is made from renewable natural sources. The production of suberinic acids requires much more energy than the production of polyphenols, which contributes to a more favorable environmental footprint of the plywood using a polyphenol-suberinic acid-lignin binder. Again, as with the fiberboard assessment, the removal of formaldehyde from consumer products is a benefit for both the manufacturers and consumers from a human health perspective.

Table 16. Comparison of the GWP of New Low-density fibreboard (Polyphenols-Suberinic acids-Lignin binder), and Conventional Low-density fibreboard (Phenolic resin binder)

	New Plywood board (Polyphenols- Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) (kg CO2 eq)	New Plywood board (Suberinic acids-Lignin binder) (kg CO2 eq)	Conventional Plywood board (Urea formaldehyde resin binder) (kg CO2 eq)
Climate change	-4322,04	-1918,316247	-1792,410537
Climate change - Fossil	352,5921	262,0853528	348,2164007
Climate change - Biogenic	-4678,87	-2182,938318	-2143,199525
Climate change - Land use and LU change	4,228617	2,536718455	2,572587054